

Enhancing Small Scale Forest Users Entrepreneurship

Mojirola Silifat Adedeji

Department of Basic and General Studies,
Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examines the roles of forestry and forest products in income generating activities especially in the face of globalization and ever increasing changes in forest ecosystem. This paper, however, highlight some measures that will enhance the entrepreneurship of forest users.

Keywords: Entrepreneurs, income generating, forest products, wood

Received: 10 March 2019

Accepted: 19 May 2019

Introduction

Forestry and forest products form a significant item of economic activities bringing substantial amount of money to rural communities and National economy. The structure of forestry, is indicative of its specialized nature as an economic activity in which man produces wood and other forest products, it has the potential of stimulating the growth and development of entrepreneurs (Olayide *et al.*, 1975). According to Olayide *et al.*, (1975) forestry is define as the management of forest for the continuous production of goods and services in responds to the need for an ultimate satisfaction of consumer's desires.

Forest Enterprises

The scope of forest enterprises in the small scale forest sector is conditioned predominantly by the demand for forest products. The diverse small scale forest enterprises include among others - Logging, Hunting, Gathering, Harvesting and Farming, Worth of mentioning are other allied economic activities such as wood

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

industries, furniture making Grafting which provide employment opportunities and generate income for the unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled forest dwellers.

Many hundreds of millions of people across the developing world trade in diverse range of timber and Non-timber forest products, every day and which are marketed primarily in local and regional domestic market (Schenker *et al.*, 2004; Osalusi *et al.*, 2011).

In many sector, small scale enterprises have long dominated economic activity, that they are faced with new challenges in the context of globalization facilitating forest entrepreneurship demand special efforts, especially if consideration is given to the many changes which forest ecosystem is currently going through worldwide. Therefore the future of small scale forest enterprises will depend on large part on the ability of the sector to adopt to change.

There is no doubting that, the Nigerian forest based enterprises operate under an atmosphere of uncertainty, thus affecting the performance of their economic role. Adeyoju (1970) opined that the effective performance of their role is impeded by a number of factors such as:-

1. The ineffectual role of entrepreneurs in many developing countries.
2. The poor development of organizational frame work for the efficient mobilization of production.
3. Inadequate capital supply for the production and distribution aspect of the forestry economy.
4. The continuous lack of technical know how and the apparent slowness of the adoption of innovation in production and distribution of forestry products.

The greatest challenge to small scale forest based entrepreneurs; arise majorly in the search for cost - effective strategies, couple with the issue of producing enough products in a context of rapidly rising urbanization, desertification and deforestation. Despite many favourable attributes, the average small scale forest based enterprise have, the enterprise still often struggle for survival in a hostile environment.

Motivational Strategies for Enhancement

The painted background of instability in the small scale forest enterprise has haunted the forest users with serious and adverse consequences on their development process. From the foregoing, it is obvious that we have a great challenge at hand which needs immediate attention by all stakeholders. One would therefore, make the following recommendations;

Recommendations

1. The small scale forest based entrepreneur should be protected from competition from large scale enterprises.
2. There should be an improvement in access to credit facilities to start and sustain their business. An efficient credit system will allow for the fulfillment of forestry role of economic activity.
3. There should be an improvement in access to technology in terms of suitable tools and equipment.
4. There should be promotion of association, cluster and cooperatives to enable small scale benefits from scale economics, in procurement of inputs, transport and promotion of products and research. According to Macqueen *et al.* (2006): the small scale entrepreneurs in the forest sector do often sense a need to connect with one another. They work together to strengthen their political voice and their bargaining power in the market. He stressed further that association help small enterprise adapt to new market opportunities and rescue their transaction cost. Elsewhere in the literature, Kazoora *et al.* (2006) revealed that, in Uganda alone, there are estimated 2000 to 3000 forest based association.
5. Education / Training will ensure the full realization of economic empowerment and strengthened their management skill. Lack of education / training perpetuate dependency, ignorance and poverty.
6. Enterprise should be linked up with secured and larger markets.
7. Lack and shortage of raw material due to seasonality, wasteful processing, poor distribution and restriction by government regulation should be eliminated.

Accordingly to White *et al.* (2007), small forest enterprises should exist legally and be granted secure tenure and access to forest resources and be taxes fairly.

8. Network of road should be developed for evacuation of products.
9. Afforestation should be encouraged by introducing the old rule of fell one plant one.
10. Encourage the forest users on preservation of biodiversity because all over the world, forest resources are increasingly scarce in particular preferred species, qualities and size. This is a growing constraint in continued activity.
11. Forest entrepreneur should be helped to identify additional products that can also contribute to a higher level of income thus allowing for saving and investment in long term forest resource development.
12. Special contribution should be given to women folks in the forest based small scale enterprises.
13. Energy and electricity should be improved, mostly to improve the comfort of work.
14. There should be provision of information and other adversary services.
15. Government policy should be reformed on forest trade for small scale enterprises because, until recently the policy had favoured large and organized forest trade thus neglecting small scale enterprises besides the poor and small scale forest enterprises should have representation in policy and decision making process

Conclusion

In summary, the potential of the forest for income generation cannot be over emphasized, but when damage is done through lack of concern for sustainability of the forest environment, then the economic activity and roles of the forest becomes low and fully aborted, but hope may be raised when necessary, measure are taken

References

- Adeyoju, S. K. (1970): "A survey of the Nigerian Timber Economy" Bulletin of Rural Economics and sociology. Vol. 5 No 1.1970.
- Kazooru C, *et al.* (2006): Forest based association as drivers for sustainable Development in Uganda, London, UK Sustainable Development Centre (SDC) and IIED.
- Macqueen, D. J. Bose 5, Bukula 5, Kazooru C., Ousman, S., Porro, N. and Weyerhaeuser, H. (2006): Working together "Forest linked small and medium enterprises associations and collective action Gate keeper series No 125 London, UK IIED
- Olayide S. A., Ogunfowora, O., Essang, S.M. and Idachaba, F. S. (1975): Element of Rural Economics Ibadan. University Press Publishing House University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Osalusi, C.S., Usman, J.M. and Pitan, O.O. (2011): Profitability of Non-Timber forest products in Rain forest Area of Ondo State Nigeria *J. Forestry Research and Management* Vol 8. Pg 27 - 33.
- Schanker A., *et al.* (2004): livelihood gains and ecological costs of NTFP dependence: - assessing the role of dependence, ecological knowledge and manhet structure in three contesting human and ecological settings in South India Germany.
- White, A., Kozak R. and Liddle, M. (2007): The large and growing role of SMFE paper presented at a side event of the 7th session of United Nation Forum of Forest (UNFF). Small forest enterprises: - Drivers of Sustainable Development New York USA 23rd April.